

Evaluation of European-wide map creation of ozone flux-based indicator POD_y for (semi-)natural vegetation

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Summary

It is widely acknowledged that ground-level ozone (O_3) affects vegetation primarily through the O_3 flux absorbed via stomata, rather than through ambient O_3 concentrations. Only the molecules entering the leaves through the stomata are harmful to plants.

Therefore, estimations of impact based on stomatal O_3 uptake (i.e. Phytotoxic Ozone Dose above a flux threshold of Y , POD_Y) that accumulates O_3 flux entering into the leaves via stomata are more appropriate than those based on O_3 concentrations. Flux-based critical levels (CLs) derived for the phytotoxic O_3 dose (POD) were introduced by the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP, or Air Convention); the last revision took place in 2017 (CLRTAP, 2024).

This paper examines the potential inclusion of Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD) for (semi-)natural vegetation in regular mapping under the ETC HE.

The POD map for the 2023 growing season for (semi-)natural vegetation is calculated based on hourly O_3 concentrations, hourly meteorological parameters such as temperature, vapour pressure deficit, solar radiation and soil hydraulic property data. The hourly O_3 concentrations are calculated by combining the monitoring data from rural background stations, chemical transport modelling data and other supplementary data (Horálek et al., 2024).

POD_1 (where 1 represents the hourly detoxification threshold) is calculated using the methodology described in the Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads and levels of the Air Convention in its 2017 revision (CLRTAP, 2024). A module to estimate phytotoxic O_3 doses from a given atmospheric O_3 exposure as developed for the Continental biogeographical region by the French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks (INERIS) has been used. This script (written in the R programming language) has been consolidated and finalized by the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI) for use in the European-wide POD spatial calculation for (semi-)natural vegetation.

In 2023, POD_1 values exceeded the CL for (semi-)natural vegetation across most of the Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic, and Pannonian regions, indicating a widespread risk to plant productivity from O_3 exposure. Only parts of Sweden, Poland, the Baltic states, Hungary and the Balkan countries remained below CLs. In the Mediterranean region, exceedances were also widespread, with non-exceedance areas mainly in eastern, central, and southern Spain, and smaller parts of Greece, Türkiye, and Cyprus.

1 Introduction

Ground-level ozone (referred to as O₃) is a secondary photochemical pollutant formed in complex chain reactions from precursors such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), carbon monoxide (CO), and methane (CH₄). These precursors originate from both natural and anthropogenic sources (The Royal Society, 2008; Anav et al., 2016; Nolle et al., 2002; Monks et al., 2015). Since O₃ formation depends on meteorological conditions, its levels fluctuate considerably from year to year (Cox, Chu 1993; Jacob et al. 1993). As a photochemical pollutant, its presence in the atmosphere is closely linked to solar radiation and high temperatures, which drive its formation (Jacob, Winner 2009; Coates et al., 2016).

O₃ is considered the most damaging common air pollutant to vegetation (Ashmore, 2005; Cieslik, 2009; Fares et al., 2017; EEA, 2020). O₃-induced damage occurs at multiple biological levels, from individual cells and leaves to whole organisms and ecosystems (Fuhrer, 2002; Ashmore, 2005; Ainsworth, 2016; Emberson et al., 2018; Mills et al., 2018). Additionally, elevated O₃ concentrations threaten terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystem services (Mills et al., 2018; Agathokleous et al., 2020; Reif et al., 2023).

Scientific consensus suggests that O₃-induced damage is more closely related to stomatal uptake than to ambient concentration (Reich, 1987; Ashmore et al., 2005; Mills et al., 2011). Although widely used, including in the EU Ambient Air quality Directives (EU, 2008, 2024), AOT40⁽¹⁾ (Accumulated Ozone exposure over a Threshold of 40 ppb) is not biologically optimal for assessing O₃ risk, as it does not consider stomatal uptake or any environmental factors affecting the O₃ uptake via stomata (Anav et al., 2016). On the contrary, a flux-based metric such as Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_y), which quantifies the accumulated stomatal O₃ flux above a threshold Y, provides a more accurate measure of O₃ exposure than AOT40 (Musselman and Massman, 1998; Nussbaum et al., 2003; Fares et al., 2010; Musselman et al., 2006; Matyssek et al., 2007; Cieslik, 2009). POD_y has been adopted in the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution, or Air Convention, (CLRTAP, 2024; Mills et al., 2011) as a preferred metric.

Currently, POD_y maps for selected crops (i.e. wheat, potato and tomato) and forest trees (i.e. beech and spruce) are regularly constructed by the ETC HE (Horálek et al., 2024). Based on the maps of POD₆ for wheat and potato, the wheat and potato yield loss due to O₃ exposure is regularly estimated (Schucht et al., 2025). However, Schucht et al. (2020) estimated the damage from O₃ on grassland in France to be at the same order of magnitude as for wheat. The aim of this report is to explore the feasibility of routine mapping of POD_y for (semi-)natural vegetation, building on earlier implementations of POD_y calculations for crops (Horálek et al., 2021) and forest trees (Vlasáková et al., 2022). The spatial estimates of POD_y for (semi-)natural vegetation might enable potential estimates of economic losses due to O₃ impacts on grass, if the production or price data for permanent grassland is available. Nevertheless, the evaluation of economic costs would be more uncertain, as some semi-natural habitats are not necessarily grazed and the assessment based solely on feed production would disregard the value of the ecosystem services they provide, for example carrying capacity for herbivorous animals (Hayes et al., 2016; Mills et al., 2013).

Semi-natural vegetation refers to vegetation not planted by humans, but influenced by human activities such as grazing, overgrazing, or selective logging, which alter the original floristic composition. It also includes abandoned cultivated areas with regenerating vegetation and secondary vegetation developing during fallow periods of shifting cultivation. Though affected by human

⁽¹⁾ The 'Accumulated Ozone exposure over a Threshold of 40 parts per billion' (AOT40), expressed in '(µg/m³) × hours', means the sum of the difference between hourly concentrations greater than 80 µg/m³ (= 40 parts per billion) and 80 µg/m³ over a given period using only the 1-hour values measured between 8:00 and 20:00 Central European Time (CET) each day (EU, 2024).

disturbance – deliberate or accidental – this vegetation may recover to a state where species composition and ecological processes resemble natural conditions. It is not artificial and does not require long-term human maintenance (Di Gregorio and Jansen, 1998).

Semi-natural habitats are shaped by long-term human use, such as grazing or traditional agriculture. They are not entirely natural, but they retain high biodiversity and cultural value. However, their persistence often depends on continued management (IUCN, 2023). These ecosystems contribute significantly to ecosystem services like pollination, pest control, water purification, and erosion prevention (García-Feced et al., 2015).

2 Methods and routines used

The calculation of the phytotoxic O₃ dose, as outlined below, follows the methodology described in the Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads and levels of the Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution Convention (CLRTAP) in its most recent available revision (CLRTAP, 2024), including some specifications presented in the Scientific background documents of this Manual (CLRTAP, 2017, 2020), as prepared by the International scientific Cooperative Programme on effects of air pollution on natural vegetation and crops of the Working Group on Effects of the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation).

Several POD_Y indicators are described in CLRTAP (2024). POD_YSPEC is a species or group of species-specific POD_Y that requires comprehensive input data and is suitable for detailed risk assessment. POD_YIAM is a vegetation-type specific POD_Y that requires fewer input data and is suitable for large-scale modelling, including integrated assessment modelling. In this report, POD_YSPEC is applied. The methodology followed is that used for calculating the species-specific POD_Y indicator (not POD_YIAM). The steps involved are presented in Table 2.1.

2.1 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose above a threshold flux Y (POD_Y) calculation

The cumulative stomatal O₃ fluxes (F_{sto}) are calculated over the course of the growing season based on ambient O₃ concentration and stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) to O₃. g_{sto} is calculated using a multiplicative stomatal conductance model proposed by Jarvis (1976) and modified by Emberson et al. (2000a) as a function of species-specific maximum g_{sto} (expressed on a single leaf-area basis), phenology, and prevailing environmental conditions (photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD)), air temperature, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and soil moisture.

Hourly averaged stomatal O₃ fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a threshold Y (expressed in mmol/m² PLA (²)) are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period during daylight hours, in order to get the phytotoxic O₃ dose above the threshold Y (POD_Y).

Table 2.1 Steps to be taken to calculate the flux-based POD_YSPEC

1	Decide on the species and biogeographical region(s) to be included.
2	Obtain the O ₃ concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period.
3	Calculate the hourly stomatal conductance of O ₃ (g _{sto}).
4	Model the hourly stomatal flux of O ₃ (F _{sto}).
5	Calculation of POD _Y SPEC from F _{sto} .

Source: CLRTAP, 2024.

Decide on the species and biogeographical region(s) to be included

According to CLRTAP (CLRTAP, 2024), due to the large diversity of (semi-)natural vegetation communities across Europe in terms of ecophysiology, life form, management practices such as grazing, cutting or fertilization regime or species composition, O₃ critical levels (CLs) have been established for widespread O₃ sensitive species representing some broad categories of (semi-)natural vegetation plant communities. However, these CLs are currently limited to grassland communities and do not cover other types of (semi-)natural vegetation. This limitation arises from the CL methodology

(²) PLA, or the projected leaf area, is the total area of the sides of the leaves that are projected towards the sun. PLA is different to the total leaf area, which accounts for both sides of the leaves.

itself, which is constrained by the availability of adequate dose–response data (González-Fernández, personal communication, September 2025).

CLs have been established for:

- Temperate perennial grasslands found in Boreal, Atlantic and Continental biogeographical regions of Europe that are dominated by grasses and forbs and have little or no tree cover, and may be grazed. The majority of vegetation species are perennials, but annual species may also be present. Parameterisations and CLs for temperate perennial grasslands may also be applicable for Pannonian and Steppic regions, but this has not been tested yet and stronger soil water limitations might be expected.
- Mediterranean annual pastures that are dominated by annual plants (grasses and forbs, including legumes). They include Dehesa annual pastures and other grazed annual pastures found in the Mediterranean region of Europe.

As shown in Table 2.2, no parameterisation and flux-based O₃ CLs are available for the Alpine, Anatolian and Black Sea biogeographical regions.

Obtaining the O₃ concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period

The O₃ concentration at the top of the canopy (nmol/m³) in a given hour H is calculated according to

$$c(z_1) = c(z_{m, O_3}) * [g(z_1) / g(z_{m, O_3})] = c(z_{m, O_3}) * [0.83 / 0.95] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.1})$$

where $c(z_1)$ is the concentration of O₃ at canopy top (ppb),
 $c(z_{m, O_3})$ denotes the O₃ concentration (ppb) at height z_m , derived from a combination of monitoring data at rural stations, the chemical transport model CAMS, and additional information (e.g. altitude). Hourly O₃ concentrations were estimated on a 2 km × 2 km grid; for more details see Chapter 3 (Input data) or Horálek et al. (2025),
 $g(z_1)$ is the O₃ concentration gradient for the height of canopy, i.e. 0.83 for (semi)-natural vegetation of 0.2 m height,
 $g(z_{m, O_3})$ is the O₃ concentration gradient for the height of O₃ measurement, i.e. 0.95 for O₃ concentration measuring at height of 2 m (i.e the height of O₃ measuring equipment)

Conversion of O₃ concentrations at measurement height to canopy height can be best achieved with an appropriate deposition model (CLRTAP, 2024; CLRTAP, 2017). However, estimating O₃ concentration at the canopy height of (semi)-natural vegetation using the deposition model is highly data demanding. Therefore, it was decided to apply a simplified method based on a tabulation of O₃ concentration gradients. This approach is also recommended and permitted by the CLRTAP (2024) in situations where detailed input data are not available.

Calculation of the hourly stomatal conductance of O₃ (g_{sto})

The basis of the approach used for calculating phytotoxic O₃ doses is the calculation of an instantaneous stomatal conductance g_{sto} in a given hour H, according to the equation

$$g_{sto} = g_{max} * [\min(f_{phen}, f_{O_3})] * f_{light} * \max[f_{min}, (f_{temp} * f_{VPD} * f_{SW})] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2})$$

where g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance in (mmol O₃ / m² PLA per second),

- g_{max} is the species-specific maximum stomatal conductance in (mmol O₃ /m² PLA per second), see Table 2.3,
- f_{phen} is the relative proportion function for the phenology for the different stage of growing,
- f_{O_3} is the relative proportion function for the influence of O₃ on stomatal flux by promoting premature senescence,
- f_{min} is the species-specific relative minimum stomatal conductance that occurs during daylight hours, see Table 2.3,
- $f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{SW}, f_{light}$ are relative proportion functions for leaf stomata respond to temperature, air humidity, soil moisture and light.

Parameters $f_{phen}, f_{light}, f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{SW}$ and f_{min} are expressed as relative proportion functions, taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} . These functions allow taking into account irradiance (f_{light}), temperature (f_{temp}), water vapour deficit at leaves level (f_{vpd}), soil moisture (f_{sw}), and phenology for the different stage of growing (f_{phen}). f_{min} is the minimum relative value of stomatal conductance during daylight.

The parameter f_{phen} is calculated according to:

$$\text{for } \begin{matrix} f_{phen} = (1 - f_{phen_a}) * [(yd - A_{start_FD})/f_{phen_1_FD}] + f_{phen_a} \\ A_{start_FD} \leq yd < (A_{star_FD} + f_{phen_1_FD}) \end{matrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.3})$$

$$\text{for } \begin{matrix} f_{phen} = 1 \\ (A_{start_FD} + f_{phen_1_FD}) \leq yd \leq (A_{end_FD} - f_{phen_4_FD}) \end{matrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.4})$$

$$\text{for } \begin{matrix} f_{phen} = (1 - f_{phen_e}) * [(A_{end} - yd)/f_{phen_4_FD}] + f_{phen_e} \\ (A_{end_FD} - f_{phen_4_FD}) < yd \leq A_{end_FD} \end{matrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.5})$$

- where yd is the year day,
- A_{start} and A_{end} are the year days for the start and end of the O₃ accumulation period respectively; parameters A_{start} and A_{end} and f_{phen_xx} are defined in the parametrization table (see Table 2.3); the subscripts FD (e.g. A_{start_FD}) refer to the fixed day,
- f_{phen_a}, f_{phen_e} is the phenology function, which consists of terms describing rate changes of g_{max} expressed as fractions (see Table 2.3),
- $f_{phen_1_FD}, f_{phen_4_FD}$ are °C days (not defined for (semi-)natural vegetation).

From the given equations and the parameterisation table (Table 2.3), it follows $f_{phen} = 1$ throughout the entire accumulation period for (semi-)natural vegetation (i.e. $f_{phen} = 1$ for the time window with the highest O₃ stomatal flux).

The parameter f_{light} is calculated according to

$$f_{light} = 1 - \text{EXP}[-(\text{light_a}) * \text{PPFD}] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.6})$$

$$\text{while } \text{PPFD} = \text{SSRD} * 0.5 * 4.5 \quad (\text{Eq. 2.7})$$

- where $PPFD$ represents the photosynthetic photon flux density (μmol/m² per second),
- $light_a$ is a light parameter (see Table 2.3),
- $SSRD$ represents the surface solar radiation downward (W/m²).

The parameter f_{temp} is calculated according to:

$$f_{temp} = \max \{f_{min}, [(T - T_{min}) / (T_{opt} - T_{min})] * [(T_{max} - T) / (T_{max} - T_{opt})]^{bt}\} \text{ when } T_{min} < T < T_{max}$$

$$= f_{min} \text{ when } T_{min} > T > T_{max} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.8})$$

while $bt = (T_{max} - T_{opt}) / (T_{opt} - T_{min})$ (Eq. 2.9)

where T_{min} , T_{max} and T_{opt} are minimum, maximum and optimum temperatures determining leaf stomata opening (see Table 2.3)

The parameter f_{VPD} is calculated according to:

$$f_{VPD} = \min\{1, \max \{f_{min}, [(1-f_{min}) * (VPD_{min} - VPD) / (VPD_{min} - VPD_{max})] + f_{min}\}\} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.10})$$

while $VPD = e_s(T) * (1 - RH)$ (Eq. 2.11)

$$e_s(T) = 0.61 \exp[17.502T / (240.97 + T)] \quad (\text{Eq. 2.12})$$

where VPD_{min} is the minimum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening, (see Table 2.3)

VPD_{max} is the maximum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening, (see Table 2.3)

T is the air temperature (°C),

RH is the relative air humidity,

$e_s(T)$ is the potential (saturation) water vapour pressure.

The parameter f_{SW} is replaced by f_{SMI} (where SMI represents Soil Moisture Index with maximum at field capacity), taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} (with 0 for soil moisture at and below wilting point), following the parameterization given in Simpson et al. (2012), similar to the plant available water (PAW) parameterization (CLRTAP, 2024; Carrasco-Molina et al., 2024). The basic equation used for f_{SW} resp. f_{SMI} is:

$$f_{SMI} = 0 \quad \text{for } SMI \leq 0$$

$$= \frac{SMI}{PAW_t} \quad \text{for } 0 < SMI \leq PAW_t$$

$$= 1 \quad \text{for } SMI > PAW_t \quad (\text{Eq. 2.13})$$

while $SMI = \frac{SWLL - PWP}{FC - PWP}$ (Eq. 2.14)

where PAW_t is the threshold amount of water in the soil available to the plants, above which stomatal conductance is at a maximum, set to 0.5 for the Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic, Pannonian bioregions and to 0.7 for the Mediterranean bioregion, respectively, (see Table 2.3)

$SWLL$ is the soil moisture in (m^3/m^3),

PWP is the permanent wilting point in (cm^3/cm^3),

FC is the field capacity in (cm^3/cm^3).

Parameter f_{SW} represents below-ground soil water, which is extremely difficult to verify due to the limited availability of measured data across Europe. Moreover, the relationship between precipitation, soil water content and soil water pressure is highly non-linear and sensitive to soil characteristics, making reliable estimation problematic. Soils and plant responses are highly heterogeneous, and simple models often fail to reflect this complexity. Therefore, using f_{SMI} provides a more practical and

robust alternative for capturing the effects of soil moisture stress in large-scale modelling (CLRTAP 2020).

The Soil Moisture Index using the EMEP methodology as described in Simpson et al. (2012) and CLRTAP (2020) is used. It is computed using soil moisture variables from the ECMWF's ERA5-Land meteorological model, which represent the water content in m³ of water per m³ of ground (m³/m³) in specific soil layers, depending on the available dataset. In addition to soil moisture, the Soil Moisture Index also takes into account the permanent wilting point and the field capacity, both taken from the JRC soil database (JRC, 2016).

The root depth of perennial grasslands, particularly forbs including legumes, in temperate European regions varies widely due to species-specific traits, environmental factors, and management practices. Grasses predominantly utilize moisture from upper soil layers, whereas legumes and forbs access deeper water reserves, especially under drought conditions (e.g. Chmelikova and Hejcman, 2012; Gerosa et al., 2017; Rojas-Botero et al., 2023; Künzi et al., 2025). Consequently, based on these studies, for soil moisture, the ECMWF's ERA5-Land variable Volume of water in soil layer 3 (i.e. 28-100 cm) has been used. For the Mediterranean area, the 7–28 cm soil layer was chosen based on the studies by De Baets et al. (2007) and Moreno et al. (2005). Root systems in this area are shallow, making the availability of water from deeper layers negligible. The soil moisture is quite a sensitive parameter in the calculation of the POD.

Modelling the hourly stomatal flux of O₃ (F_{sto})

Once the hourly stomatal conductance of O₃ (g_{sto}) and all relevant variables are computed, the stomatal flux of O₃ (F_{sto}) can be calculated, based on the assumption that the concentration of O₃ at the top of the canopy represents a reasonable estimate of the concentration at the upper surface of the laminar layer for a sunlit upper canopy leaf. F_{sto} is calculated according to the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation) methodology, thus the fraction of the O₃ taken up by the stomata is given using a combination of the stomatal conductance, the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance and the leaf surface resistance. The hourly stomatal flux in a given hour H is calculated according to

$$F_{sto} = c(z_1) * g_{sto} * \frac{r_c}{r_b + r_c} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.15})$$

where F_{sto} is the hourly stomatal flux of O₃ in (nmol/m² PLA per second)
 $c(z_1)$ is the concentration of O₃ at canopy top in (nmol/m³)
 r_b is the quasi-laminar resistance in (s/m)
 r_c is the leaf surface resistance in (s/m)
 g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance in (m/s),

while $r_c = 1/(g_{sto} + g_{ext})$ (Eq. 2.16)

$$r_b = 1.3 * 150 * \sqrt{\frac{L}{u(z_1)}} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.17})$$

where g_{ext} is the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance in (m/s), equal to 1/2500 m/s
 $u(z_1)$ is the wind speed at height z_1 (z_1 is the canopy top)
 L is the cross-wind leaf dimension (2 cm, see Table 2.3)

while $u(z_1) = \frac{u^*}{k} * \ln\left(\frac{z_1 - d}{z_0}\right)$ (Eq. 2.18)

where k is the von Kármán constant (equal to 0.41)
 d is the displacement height usually assumed as 2/3 of the canopy height,
 z_1 is the top of the canopy
 z_0 is the roughness length usually assumed as 1/10 of the canopy height
 u^* is the friction velocity

Box 1 Conversion of stomatal conductance g_{sto} and O_3 concentration to units demanded for POD_Y calculation

Stomatal conductance g_{sto} has to be converted from $mmol/m^2$ per second to m/s (since all the resistances are expressed in the unit of m/s). At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure (1.013×10^5 Pa), the conversion is made by dividing the conductance in $mmol/m^2$ per second by 41 000 to give conductance in m/s .

To convert the **O_3 concentration (C)** at canopy height from $\mu g/m^3$ resp. ppb to $nmol/m^3$, the following equation should be used:

$$C [nmol/m^3] = C [ppb] * P/(R \cdot T) = C [\mu g/m^3] / 2 * P/(R \cdot T) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.19})$$

where P is the atmospheric pressure in Pa,
 R is the universal gas constant of 8.31447 J/mol per Kelvin
 T is the air temperature in Kelvin.

At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure (1.013×10^5 Pa), the concentration in ppb should be multiplied by 41.56 to calculate the concentration in $nmol/m^3$.

Source: CLRTAP, 2024.

Calculation of POD_Y from F_{sto}

Hourly averaged stomatal O_3 fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a Y threshold are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period using the following equation:

$$POD_Y = \sum_n (F_{sto}(n) - Y) \cdot \frac{3600}{10^6} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.20})$$

while Y (for (semi-)natural ecosystems) = 1 $nmol/m^2$ PLA per second

where POD_Y is the phytotoxic O_3 dose related to the threshold Y , in [$mmol/m^2$ PLA],
 $F_{sto}(n)$ is the hourly O_3 flux in the hour n of the accumulation period.

The value Y (in ($nmol/m^2$ PLA per second)) is subtracted from each hourly averaged F_{sto} (in ($nmol/m^2$ PLA per second)) value and the F_{sto} (after the subtracting of Y) is accumulated only when $F_{sto} > Y$, during daylight hours (when global radiation is more than 50 W/m^2). The value is then converted to hourly fluxes by multiplying by 3 600 and to $mmol$ by dividing by 10^6 to get the stomatal O_3 flux in $mmol/m^2$ PLA.

2.2 Parametrization

For temperate perennial grasslands, two parameterizations for the Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonia and Steppic biogeographical regions are available (for grass and for forbs including legumes). In this report, the one for forbs including legumes was used, as recommended by the CLRTAP (2024), to serve as a general indicator of the risk of O_3 effects on grassland habitats. Table 2.2 presents the

parameterisation available and applied for different biogeographical regions. Table 2.3 presents the parameterisation of the (semi-)natural vegetation as used in this report.

Table 2.2 Summary of the parameterisation for PODySPEC calculations for semi-natural vegetation

Biographic regions in Europe (EEA, 2016)	(Semi-)natural vegetation ^(a)
Alpine > 50°	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Alpine < 50°	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Anatolian	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Arctic	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Atlantic	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Boreal	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Continental	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Pannonian	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Steppic	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic
Mediterranean	Mediterranean
Black Sea	Mediterranean

^(a) Regions for which parameterisation for (semi-)natural vegetation according to CLRTAP (CLRTAP 2024; CLRTAP 2020b) is available are highlighted in green. Regions without parameterisation are highlighted in red. These are presented in maps of POD₁ (Map 4.1) using semi-transparent colours (while the calculation in these areas was based on the most closely related available parameterisation).

Table 2.3 Parameterisation for POD₁SPEC calculations for sunlit leaves at the top of the canopy for representative O₃-sensitive (semi-)natural vegetation species.

Parameter	Units	(Semi-)natural vegetation	
		Atlantic, Boreal, Continental (Pannonia, Steppic) Perennial grasslands (Forbs including legumes)	Mediterranean Annual pastures (Legume spp.)
g _{max}	mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	210	782
f _{min}	fraction	0.1	0.02
light_a	-	0.02	0.013
T _{min}	°C	10	8
T _{opt}	°C	22	22
T _{max}	°C	36	33
VPD _{max}	kPa	1.75	2.2
VPD _{min}	kPa	4.5	4.3
PAW _t		0.5	0.7
A _{start_FD}	day of year	91 (1 st April)	32 (1 st February)
A _{end_FD}	day of year	273 (30 th October)	181 (30 th June)
Time window length ^(a)	days	90	45
Leaf dimension	cm	4	2
Canopy height	m	0.2	0.2
f _{phen_a}	fraction	1	1
f _{phen_b}	fraction	1	1
f _{phen_c}	fraction	1	1
f _{phen_d}	fraction	1	1
f _{phen_e}	fraction	1	1

^(a) The time window represents the 90-day and the 45-day accumulation period with the highest stomatal O₃ flux. This 90-day period will fall within the range of 1 April to 30 September (i.e. within the range of A_{start_FD} to A_{end_FD}) for the Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, and Steppic regions. The 45-day period will fall within the range of 1 February and 30 June for the Mediterranean region.

Source: CLRTAP, 2024; CLRTAP, 2020, Carrasco-Molina et al., 2024

Map 2.1 shows the geographical distribution of the biogeographical regions in Europe.

Map 2.1 Biogeographical regions in Europe

Source: EEA, 2016.

2.3 Ozone gridded data estimation

The hourly O₃ gridded data (used in the POD_γ mapping) are calculated by combining the monitoring, chemical transport modelling and other supplementary data. The methodology for this combination is a linear regression model followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that model (residual kriging), as routinely used in the hourly O₃ mapping applied in the regular POD_γ for crops and trees map creation (Horálek et al., 2025). Interpolation is therefore carried out according to the relation:

$$\hat{Z}(s_0) = c + a_1X_1(s_0) + a_2X_2(s_0) + \dots + a_nX_n(s_0) + \eta(s_0) \quad (\text{Eq. 2.211})$$

where $\hat{Z}(s_0)$ is the estimated value of the air pollution indicator at the point s_0 ,
 $X_1(s_0), X_2(s_0), \dots, X_n(s_0)$ are n number of individual supplementary variables at the point s_0 ,
 c, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are $n+1$ parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the points of measurement,
 $\eta(s_0)$ is the spatial interpolation of the residuals of the linear regression model at the point s_0 calculated based on the residuals at the points of measurement.

The gridded data are calculated for hourly values at 2 km resolution, based on rural background measurements (see Section 3.1). The supplementary variables used are chemical transport model output, surface solar radiation and altitude (see Sections 3.2-3.4).

3 Input data

3.1 Air quality monitoring data

Air quality monitoring station data have been extracted from the official EEA Air Quality e-Reporting database (EEA, 2025). The data come from the E1a data flow, i.e. these are the official data as reported by the EEA's member and cooperating states. This data set has been supplemented with British rural stations from the Defra database (Defra, 2024), which are not reported to the Air Quality e-Reporting database. Only data from stations classified as rural background have been considered. Ozone hourly data for 2023 have been used. In total, data from 602 monitoring stations have been applied (including 22 British stations from the Defra database). These O₃ monitoring data have been used for the O₃ hourly gridded data estimation, together with the O₃ hourly modelling data and other supplementary data. For details, see Horálek et al. (2025).

3.2 Chemical transport model output

The chemical dispersion modelling data used for the O₃ hourly gridded data estimation (see Section 2.2) are the CAMS Ensemble Forecast modelling O₃ hourly data (CAMS, 2024). The output data of the CAMS modelling are provided by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) at a regional scale over Europe. The European regional production consists of an ensemble of eleven air quality models run operationally. The model forecasts of the individual models are combined into the Ensemble Forecast by taking the median of all eleven models. For details, see ECMWF (2024). All the models used in the CAMS ensemble products were run using the CAMS-REG emissions (Kuenen et al., 2024) and the meteorology (i.e., the weather forecast) provided by the European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) operationally. The resolution of the modelling data is 0.1°×0.1° which is around 10×10 km. For details, see Horálek et al. (2025).

3.3 Meteorological data

The meteorological data used are the ECMWF data extracted from the CDS (Climate Data Store, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home>). Hourly data for 2023 are used. Most of the data come from the reanalysed data set ERA5-Land at 0.1°×0.1° resolution, namely the indicators:

Surface solar radiation – variable “Surface solar radiation downwards”

Temperature – variable “2m temperature”

Surface pressure – variable “surface_pressure”

Relative humidity (RH) is derived by means of the saturated water vapour pressure (e_s) as a function of “2m temperature” T and “2m dew point temperature” (D) according to relation

$$RH = \frac{e_D}{e_T} = \frac{0.611 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot D}{240.97 + D}\right)}{0.611 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot T}{240.97 + T}\right)} = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot D}{240.97 + D}\right)}{\exp\left(\frac{17.502 \cdot T}{240.97 + T}\right)}, \quad (\text{Eq. 3.1})$$

where D is the dew point temperature at 2 meter height,
 T is the temperature at 2 meter height.

In the coastal areas (where the data from ERA5-Land are not available), the same parameters from the reanalysed data set ERA5 at 0.25°x0.25° resolution are applied. Additionally to this, the following data (not available in the ERA5-Land data set) from the ERA5 data set are also used:

Friction velocity – variable “Friction velocity”, also known as the shear-stress velocity (in m/s).

All meteorological data were re-gridded and converted into the reference EEA 2 km grid, in the ETRS89-LAEA5210 projection.

3.4 Altitude

The altitude data field (in m) of Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) was used, with an original grid resolution of 15×15 arcseconds from U.S. Geological Survey Earth Resources Observation and Science, see Danielson et al. (2011). The original data were converted into the 2 km grid resolution of the ETRS 1989 LAEA projection.

3.5 Soil hydraulic properties

The soil water content data are also ERA5-Land ECWMF data downloaded from the CDS (Climate Data Store, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home>). The indicator is:

Soil water – variable “Volumetric soil water layer 3”, i.e. layer of 28-100 cm for (semi-)natural vegetation in the Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic, and Pannonian biogeographical regions and “Volumetric soil water layer 2”, i.e. layer of 7-28 cm for (semi-)natural vegetation in the Mediterranean area

JRC data labelled as "Maps of indicators of soil hydraulic properties for Europe" at 1×1 km² resolution are used; the dataset and maps have been downloaded from the European Soil Data Centre JRC (2016). The following indicators are used:

Wilting Point – water content at wilting point (cm³/cm³)

Field Capacity – water content at field capacity (cm³/cm³)

4 Results – maps of POD₁ for (semi-)natural vegetation

Map 4.1 presents the final maps of Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₁) for (semi-)natural vegetation in 2023, separately for two groups of biogeographical regions. The reason for the separate presentation of the two groups of biogeographical regions is the different both parametrisation and values of critical levels (CLs) in these two groups of regions. For the CLs for the (semi-)natural vegetation, see Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 POD₁SPEC critical levels (CL) for (semi-)natural vegetation as determined by CLRTAP (CLRTAP, 2024)

Biogeographical region	Species	Effect parameter	CL (mmol/m ² PLA)
Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic, Pannonian	Temperate perennial grassland	Flower number	6.6
Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic, Pannonian	Temperate perennial grassland	Above-ground biomass	10.2
Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic, Pannonian	Temperate perennial grassland	Total biomass	16.2
Mediterranean	Mediterranean annual pasture	Flower/seed biomass	10.8
Mediterranean	Mediterranean annual pasture	Above-ground biomass	16.9

The areas in Map 4.1 with POD₁ values below the CL for flower number (for Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic and Panonian biogeographical regions) or CL for flower/seed biomass (for Mediterranean biogeographical region) are marked in green. The areas with POD₁ values in between CLs for flower number (for Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic and Panonian biogeographical regions) or flower/seed biomass (for Mediterranean biogeographical region) and above-ground biomass are marked in yellow. For Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic and Panonian biogeographical regions, the areas with POD₁ values in between CLs for above-ground biomass and total biomass are marked in orange and the areas with POD₁ values above the CL for total biomass are marked in red and dark red. In the Mediterranean biogeographical region, the areas with POD₁ values above the CL for above-ground biomass are marked in orange, red and dark red.

Since no parametrization for (semi-)natural vegetation in the Alpine, Anatolian, Arctic and Black Sea biogeographical regions is available (see Section 2.2), these areas are marked in semi-transparent colours.

High values of POD₁ can be found across various areas of Europe, since POD₁ is dependent not only on O₃ levels but also on the environmental conditions and plant phenology. For example, higher POD₁ values can occur in areas with lower O₃ concentrations but favourable conditions for the stomatal conductance. On the other hand, the lowest levels of POD₁ usually occur in areas with lower O₃ concentrations, such as northern European regions, and/or in areas where environmental conditions limit the O₃ stomatal conductance such as dry and warm areas, including parts of the southern and south-eastern Europe.

In 2023, POD₁ values exceeded the CLs (critical levels) for (semi-)natural vegetation for flower numbers and above-ground biomass across most of the Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Steppic, and Pannonian regions, suggesting a widespread risk to plant productivity from O₃ exposure (Map 4.1). Only a few areas remained below any of the established CLs, including the lowest threshold related to flower number (6.6 mmol/m² PLA). These non-exceedance areas were limited to a large region in Sweden and several smaller, fragmented zones in Poland, the Baltic states, Hungary, Serbia, Bulgaria, Romania etc.

Map 4.1 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₁) for (semi-)natural vegetation, rural maps, 2023

Note: As with the maps of other vegetation-related indicators (Horálek et al., 2024), only monitoring data from the rural background stations are used in the mapping. Thus, the maps are representative for rural areas only, and the estimated POD₁ values in the urban areas are based on the O₃ modelling data without adjustment by the monitoring data from the urban and suburban stations.

Regarding the Mediterranean area, exceedance of the lower CL associated with the effect on flower and seed biomass (10.8 mmol/m² PLA) was found in most of the mapped area, while the highest CL for above-ground biomass (16.9 mmol/m² PLA) was exceeded in parts of the Iberian Peninsula, Italy, parts of the Balkan countries (particularly in almost whole Greece) and the western part of Türkiye. In the Mediterranean area, no exceedance of the CLs was observed in larger parts of eastern, central, and southern Spain, as well as in smaller areas in Greece, Türkiye, and Cyprus.

5 Conclusions

This paper examines the potential inclusion of the Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD) for (semi-)natural vegetation in regular mapping under the ETC HE, following the earlier inclusion of the POD for crops (Horálek et al., 2021) and POD for trees (Vlasáková et al., 2022). Such an inclusion would be beneficial, as the flux-based POD_Y metrics (i.e. POD above a threshold flux Y) are generally preferred in risk assessment over the concentration-based exposure metrics like AOT40 indexes.

Maps of POD_1 for (semi-)natural vegetation have been prepared, for a uniform species O_3 flux threshold of $Y = 1 \text{ nmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA per second}$. The methodology applied is documented in detail and the input data used are fully detailed. POD calculation has been performed using routines developed earlier by INERIS (POD parametrisation for the Continental biogeographical region) and has been consolidated and finalized by the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI) for use in the European-wide POD spatial calculation for (semi-)natural vegetation. This tool follows the methodology described in the Manual on Methodologies and Criteria for Modelling and Mapping Critical Loads and Levels and Air Pollution Effects, Risks, and Trends of the Air Convention in its most recent available revision dated 2024 (CLRTAP, 2024).

The POD maps have been constructed at 0.1° resolution, the final outputs were transferred to the 2 km resolution of the EEA layout as routinely used in other regular maps of vegetation-related indicators. It can be concluded that the inclusion of POD for (semi-)natural vegetation in routine mapping along with the other maps already produced is technically feasible.

From a technical perspective, the methodology, technical capacity, and input data required for routine mapping of POD_1 for (semi-)natural vegetation are already in place. However, the decision on whether such maps will be included in routine reporting depends on the strategic priorities of the EEA and its stakeholders.

The current CLs for O_3 are likely more relevant for biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services than for assessing the economic value of fodder production (González-Fernández, personal communication, September 2025). Nevertheless, the practical value of including POD_1 for (semi-)natural vegetation in the routinely mapped air quality indicators as presented in regular mapping reports (Horálek et al., 2024, 2025) is closely linked to the ability to quantify the impacts of O_3 exposure in economic terms. As highlighted in recent analysis (Schucht et al., 2020; Schucht et al., 2024), the lack of harmonised production or price data for permanent grasslands at the European level presents a barrier to estimating economic losses due to O_3 exposure. Although such data may exist in some countries, there is currently no plan to collect them systematically.

In summary, while the routine production of POD_1 maps for (semi-)natural vegetation is technically achievable, its implementation as a standard activity should be aligned with the EEA priorities, particularly regarding the integration of such data into broader assessments of biodiversity conservation and/or economic loss.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
AOT40	Accumulated Ozone exposure over a Threshold of 40 ppb	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0050
CHMI	Czech Hydrometeorological Institute	https://www.chmi.cz/?l=en
CL	Critical Level	https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/11850/publikationen/123_2024_texte_manual_on_methodologies_and_criteria.pdf
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution	https://unece.org/environment-policy/air
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	https://www.ecmwf.int/
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme	https://www.emep.int/
ETC HE	European Topic Centre on Human health and the environment	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
EU	European Union	https://european-union.europa.eu
FD	fixed day	
ICP Vegetation	International Cooperative Programme on Effects of Air Pollution on Natural Vegetation and Crops	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/
INERIS	French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks	https://www.ineris.fr/en
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature	https://iucn.org
LAI	Leaf Area Index	https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/11850/publikationen/123_2024_texte_manual_on_methodologies_and_criteria.pdf
NILU	Norwegian Institute for Air Research	https://www.nilu.no/
POD	Phytotoxic Ozone Dose	
POD _y	Phytotoxic Ozone Dose above a threshold Y	
POD ₃	Phytotoxic Ozone Doze above a threshold of 3 nmol/m ² PLA per second	https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/11850/publikationen/123_2024_texte_manual_on_methodologies_and_criteria.pdf
PPFD	Photosynthetic Photon Flux Density	
SMI	Soil Moisture Index	
spp.	species	
VPD	Vapour Pressure Deficit	

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